

APPENDIX B – PARTICIPANT CHARACTERIZATION QUESTIONNAIRE

Investigating the Online Recruitment and Selection Journey of Novice Software Engineers: Anti-patterns and Recommendations

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1. What is your name?

2. How old are you?

3. In terms of gender, how do you identify?

Male

Female

Non-binary

Prefer not to inform

Other:

4. What is your academic background?

Bachelor's degree

Specialization

Master's degree

Doctorate

MBA

Other:

5. Based on the previous answer, what is your field of study?

6. In which company do you currently work?

7. How long have you been working at your current company?

8. How many employees does your company currently have?

9. What is your current position/job function?

10. How long have you been involved in recruitment and selection activities (excluding the online process)?

11. How long have you been involved in online recruitment and selection activities?